

Isoquinoline Derivatives: Part XXI. Synthesis of Some α , γ -Bis-(3-Alkyl 3,4-Dihydroisoquinolyl-1-) Propanes and Related Compounds*

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Synthesis of some bisdihydroisoquinolines in which two isoquinoline nuclei with CH_3 or C_3H_7 substitutions at 3,3'-positions are being linked through the 1,1'-positions by $-(\text{CH}_2)_3$ -group and cyclisation of ethyl N- α -propyl- β -phenyl glutaramate to afford the corresponding isoquinoline ester are reported.

As an extension of the work communicated earlier by Ghosh¹ and his co-workers^{1,2} from this laboratory, the synthesis of a series of bisdihydroisoquinolines (V), in which two isoquinoline nuclei with alkyl (e.g., CH_3 , C_3H_7) substitutions at 3,3'-positions are being linked through the 1,1'-positions by a chain of three methylene groups, is now being reported. These compounds are expected to exert some spasmolytic activity, since isoquinolines with a methyl substitution at the 3-position and 1,1'-bisisoquinoline derivatives are already known as spasmolytics³⁻⁶. Further, the synthesis of these compounds appears to be interesting in view of the reported failure in synthesising similar type of compounds by Child and Pyman⁷.

During the preparation of the intermediate (IVa) required for the synthesis of (Va) it has been observed that when α -methyl- β -phenyl ethyl amine⁸ (I; $\text{R} = \text{CH}_3$) is heated with diethyl glutarate (II) for about 16 hrs a mixture of amides e.g., ethyl N- α -methyl- β -phenyl glutaramate (IIIa) and glutardi- α -methyl- β -phenethyl amide (IVa) is formed. These amides have been isolated individually from the mixture and the structure of glutaramate (IIIa) has been confirmed by comparing it with its authentic specimen⁹, prepared by the interaction of γ -carbethoxy butyryl chloride¹⁰ with the amine (I; $\text{R} = \text{CH}_3$). It has also been recorded that when the amine (I; $\text{R} = \text{CH}_3$) reacts with the ester (II) in the ratio 1 : 1 the major compound is (IIIa), whereas when the amine (I; $\text{R} = \text{CH}_3$) and the ester (II) are made to react in the ratio 3 : 1, the compound (IVa) is formed in greater yield. The

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compound (IIIa) on further heating with β -phenethylamine (I; R = H) in equimolecular ratio has afforded 1-(α -methyl- β -phenethylamido)-3-(β -phenethylamido)-propane (IVb). Subsequently the amide (IVb) has been subjected to Bischler-Napieralski reaction in presence of PPA and POCl₃ at 130° to furnish α -(3-methyl-3,4-dihydroisoquinolyl-1)- γ -(3,4-dihydroisoquinolyl-1)-propane (Vb). Similar reaction of the amide (IVa) with PPA at 135–40° resulted in the formation of α,γ -bis-(3-methyl-3,4-dihydroisoquinolyl-1)-propane (Va).

The work is further extended with a propyl substitution at 3,3'-positions of the bis-dihydroisoquinoline as indicated in structure (Vc). According to the previous observation the corresponding glutaramate (IIIb) and the diamide (IVc) have been isolated from the reaction of the amine¹¹ (I; R = C₃H₇) and ester (II). Cyclisation of the diamide (IVc) with PPA and POCl₃ at 130–35° has furnished α,γ -bis-(3-propyl-3,4-dihydroisoquinolyl-1)-propane (Vc). The glutaramate (IIIb), on the other hand, on cyclisation with POCl₃ in benzene gives ethyl-3-propyl-3,4-dihydroisoquinoline-1-butyrate (VI). The cyclisation of the other glutaramate (IIIa) has been recorded by the present authors in an earlier communication⁹.

EXPERIMENTAL

All melting and boiling points are uncorrected. UV absorption spectra were taken in ethanol solution and measured in a Hilger Spectrophotometer, model H 700, using quartz cells.

Ethyl N- α -methyl- β -phenethyl glutaramate (IIIa) and glutardi- α -methyl- β -phenethyl amide (IVa): In a three necked flask protected from moisture, fitted with a mercury sealed stirrer, a reflux condenser and a separating funnel, diethyl glutarate (II, 20 g.) was heated to 175°. To that α -methyl- β -phenethylamine (I, R = CH₃; 40 g.) was added dropwise in course of 1 hr under stirring. The mixture was then heated at 175–80° for 16 hrs more,

11. S. K. Gangopadhyay, Isoquinoline Derivatives as Possible Amoebicides, D.Phil. Thesis, Calcutta University, 1962, 72.

the semisolid mass thus formed was poured into ether and the separated solid product was filtered, dried and crystallised from dilute ethanol to afford (IVa) in colourless microcrystalline powder, m.p. 134–5° (Found : C, 75.31; H, 8.09; N, 7.73. $C_{23}H_{30}N_2O_2$ requires C, 75.41; H, 8.19; N, 7.65%).

The ethereal filtrate on concentration was distilled in vacuo to furnish a liquid, b.p. 218–20°/10 mm. which was characterised as (IIIa) on comparison with the b.p. 215–20°/10–12 mm. and the analytical data of its authentic specimen⁹, reported earlier.

1-(α -Methyl- β -phenethylamido)-3-(β -phenethylamido)-propane (IVb) : A mixture of the compound (IIIa; 12.5 g.) and β -phenethylamine (I, R = H; 6 g.) was heated under stirring at 180–5° for 4 hr in the absence of moisture and kept overnight. The resultant solid product was washed with acetone, filtered and the residue was crystallised from dilute ethanol to furnish (IVb) in colourless microcrystals (14 g.), m.p. 128–30°. (Found : C, 74.84; H, 8.01; N, 7.88. $C_{22}H_{28}N_2O_2$ requires C, 75.00; H, 7.95; N, 7.95%).

α -(3-Methyl-3,4-dihydroisoquinoyl-1)- γ -(3,4-dihydroisoquinolyl-1)-propane (Vb) : To P_2O_5 (80 g.) taken in a three necked flask, orthophosphoric acid (80 per cent; 50 ml.) was added, dropwise in course of 15 min. The product was then heated at 100–5° for 2 hr under stirring, brought to room temperature and at that stage $POCl_3$ (10 ml.) was added, when frothing occurred. Subsequently (IVb; 8 g.) was added to the above reaction mixture and heated at 130° for 6 hr. The product was then decomposed with ice, treated with charcoal and filtered. The filtrate was basified with ammonium hydroxide to afford a brown coloured oil which was extracted with ether and dried (Na_2SO_4). The dark coloured oil after removal of ether was distilled at 95–7°/1 mm to furnish (Vb) as a colourless liquid; λ_{max} 250 $m\mu$ (log ϵ , 4.19). (Found : C, 83.61; H, 7.41; N, 8.92. $C_{22}H_{24}N_2$ requires C, 83.54; H, 7.59; N, 8.86%).

The dipicrate was crystallised from ethanol in yellow microcrystalline powder, m.p. 205–6° (Found : N, 14.78. $C_{22}H_{24}N_2$, $2C_6H_3N_3O_7$ requires N, 14.47%).

α,γ -Bis-(3-methyl-3,4-dihydroisoquinolyl-1)-propane (Va) : To polyphosphoric acid [from P_2O_5 (50 g.) and orthophosphoric acid (80 per cent; 30 ml.)], compound (IVa; 5 g.) was added and the mixture was heated under stirring at 135–40° for 10 hr. The black viscous mass was decomposed with ice and water, treated with charcoal and filtered. The filtrate on basification with ammonium hydroxide furnished a brown coloured oil which was extracted with ether, washed with water and dried (Na_2SO_4). The residual deep brown liquid after removal of ether was distilled in vacuo to afford (Va), b.p. 95–6°/1 mm; λ_{max} 250 $m\mu$ (log ϵ , 4.14) (Found : C, 83.68; H, 7.63; N, 8.57. $C_{23}H_{26}N_2$ requires C, 83.64; H, 7.87; N, 8.48%).

The dipicrate was crystallised from ethanol in shining yellow microcrystals, m.p. 213–4°. (Found : N, 14.37; $C_{23}H_{26}N_2$, $2C_6H_3N_3O_7$ requires, N, 14.21%).

Ethyl N - α -propyl- β -phenethyl glutaramate (IIIb) and glutardi- α -propyl- β -phenethyl amide (IVc) : Diethylglutarate (II, 20 g.) was treated with α -propyl- β -phenylethylamine¹¹ (I, R = C_3H_7 ; 36 g.) and following the same procedure described in case of the reaction of

(I, R = CH₃) with (II), the compound (IVc; 7 g.), m.p. 148° (Found : N, 6.58. C₂₇H₃₃N₂O₂ requires N, 6.63%) and compound (IIIb; 12 g.), b.p. 210–11°/10 mm. (Found : N, 4.50. C₁₈H₂₇NO₃ requires N, 4.59%) were isolated.

α,γ-Bis-(3-propyl-3,4-dihydroisoquinolyl-1)-propane (Vc): To a mixture of PPA [prepared from P₂O₅ (100 g.) and orthophosphoric acid (80 per cent; 60 ml)] and POCl₃ (12 ml.), the compound (IVc; 10 g.) was added gradually and then heated with stirring at 130–35° for 8 hr. The reaction product was then worked up by the usual procedure to afford (Vc; 1 g.), b.p. 97–8°/1–1.2 mm. as light yellow liquid; λ_{max} 258 mμ (log ε 4.26) (Found : N, 7.31. C₂₇H₃₄N₂ requires N, 7.25%).

The dipicrate was crystallised from ethanol in lemon yellow crystals, m.p. 210–2° (Found : N, 13.31. C₂₇H₃₄N₂, 2C₆H₃N₃O₇ requires N, 13.27%).

Ethyl 3-propyl-3,4-dihydroisoquinoline-1-butylate (VI): A mixture of the compound (IIIb; 10 g.), dry benzene (100 ml.) and POCl₃ (10 ml.), protected from moisture, was heated under reflux for about 4 hr. The benzene was distilled under reduced pressure. The dark coloured viscous mass left in the flask was cooled and decomposed with ice, treated with charcoal and filtered. The filtrate was then basified with ammonium hydroxide in cold to afford a green coloured oil which was extracted with ether, washed with brine and dried (Na₂SO₄). The residual liquid left after removal of ether was distilled in vacuo to afford a green coloured liquid, b.p. 94–5°/0.1 mm; yield 0.5 g. (Found : C, 75.13; H, 8.63; N, 4.72. C₁₈H₂₅NO₂ requires C, 75.26; H, 8.71; N, 4.87%). It gives hydroxamate test for ester.

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